

UNDERSTANDING CYBERCRIMES AGAINST FEMALE STUDENTS OF KASHMIR UNIVERSITY: A MIXED METHOD STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Technological advancements of the 20th century not only transformed female's access to information and virtual interactions but has led to rise in cybercrimes, Criminal acts targeting individuals or groups using digital technology to inflict mental harm directly or indirectly. These cybercrimes not only pose a higher risk of targeting females , who are often viewed as vulnerable by legal system, but also inflict severe physical, sexual, psychological, and economic harm on them .This research delves into cybercrimes among female university students in Kashmir and its subsequent repercussions. Employing a mixed method approach, the study amassed quantitative data from 250 female students out of which 10 female students were considered for qualitative approach from the same group. Despite cybercrimes not being alarmingly high in the area the lack of computer proficiency and cyber laws leaves females vulnerable to offences. The psychological reverberations of cybercrimes are profound, precipitating depression, anxiety, and a withdrawal from virtual engagements. Thus the study underscores pressing need to enhance cyber safety and legal protections for females within Kashmir University.

Practice impact statement: *This study highlights the urgent need for targeted interventions to bolster cyber literacy and resilience among female university students in Kashmir. By fostering digital safety awareness and strengthening institutional support systems, stakeholders can create a safer online environment, empowering women to engage confidently in the digital sphere without fear of exploitation or harm.*

Keywords - Cybercrimes; Female students; Technology; Psychological trauma etc.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The pervasive integration of technology into human existence underscores its indispensable role in contemporary life. From desktops to smartphones, technological devices have become inseparable companions, catering to diverse needs and demands. The evolution of the internet epitomizes this technological revolution, transforming from a rarity in the 1990s to an indispensable utility in the modern era (Chudasama & Solanki, 2021; Mansi & Agarwal, 2020; Singh et al., 2014). In today's digitally connected world, access to the internet has transitioned from a luxury to a necessity, empowering individuals to fulfil myriad responsibilities from professional endeavours to domestic chores (Sawaneh, 2020; Zahoor & Razi, 2020). According to Kaur (2015), these factors have considerably influenced the rise of internet. The advent of smartphones, fuelled by affordable data plans, has democratized internet access, bridging the digital divide and expanding connectivity to even the remotest corners. However, this exponential growth in internet usage has also exposed a darker underbelly, the escalation of cybercrimes (Khudhair, 2021).

The usage of the internet has associated costs and some negative implications (Ahmed et al., 2017; Kaur, 2015; Mansi & Agarwal, 2020; Sawaneh, 2020). For instance, Hacking is a major defect. The internet's global reach has given rise to cybercrime as a novel form of criminal activity (Mansi & Agarwal, 2020; Rao et al., 2016). However the internet cannot be held accountable as it is neutral (Joshi & Singh, 2013) and does not contribute to cybercrimes on its own; but it offers an avenue and opportunity for potential cybercriminals to advance their criminal objectives using highly advanced and sophisticated tools (Kundi et al., 2014). Hence, it has created a sense of alarm and precariousness among various users. Cybercrime encompass a gamut of nefarious activities, including cyber stalking, harassment and dissemination of derogatory content, posing grave threats to public safety (Backe et al., 2018; Chaudhary, 2019). Despite their increasing prevalence, cybercrimes often go unreported, with only a fraction making it to official records, amplifying the vulnerability of females and children in cyberspace (Halder & Jaishankar, 2011; Meena et al., 2020).

II. Theoretical background: Engaging feminist criminologist Approach

Although statistical studies reveal gender differences in crime, these distinctions are seldom explicitly discussed and are intertwined with feminist perspectives on crime (Chesney-Lind, 2020). Feminist epistemology of crime considers the unequal power dynamics between males

and females, as well as differences in their perceptions and experiences of the world, in its examination of crime and gender (Chesney-Lind, 2020; Lynch, 2018). In perceptions of risk or crime, gender makes a difference. Scholars such as Choi and Merlo (2021) and Davis and Dossetor (2010) show that gender differences significantly impact how crime is perceived. Gender socialization, for example, plays a crucial role in shaping differences in how crime is perceived. First, male children are encouraged to be tough and resilient, female children are often expected to be shy and submissive. Females are taught to suppress their voices due to the fear of stigmatization (Lazarus et al., 2022). Consequently, they become accustomed to suppressing the important issues by claiming that ‘nothing happened’ (Saha & Srivastava, 2014). Second, from a very early age, females are socialized differently compared to boys which led to the perception of their own vulnerability and lack of confidence in facing potential threats in public spaces. Gender differences arising from unequal power dynamics between males and females result in various aspects and stances within society (Burgess-proctor; Chesney-lind, 2020). Thus, the feminist perspective places emphasis on the way we socialize boys and girls, through which they hold different powers in societies and view and perceive crimes differently. This view helps us dig deeper and reach the genesis of the crime by which girls and boys are taught to react differently to these crimes, which is why it is very important to know why girls are more vulnerable to these crimes as compared to boys.

Research on internet-based crimes indicates that sexually motivated offenses, such as rape threats and online sexual harassment, evoke greater fear among females as compared to males (Eckert, 2018; Walker & Sleath, 2017) and most victimized by psychological crimes on the Internet (e.g., females) are those most fearful of these crimes. Gender identity significantly contributes to the difference in fear of crime between males and females (Choi & Merlo, 2021). So gender difference is crucial in crime perception for developing effective strategies to address safety concerns. Understanding the impact of socialization, power dynamics, and fear levels can inform targeted interventions that benefit both males and females in society.

III. Study Context

In Kashmir, females face violence within their homes and in public spaces. This includes molestation, unwanted staring, eve teasing, kidnapping, rape, and human trafficking (Zeeshan & Aliefendioğlu, 2024). Throughout history, women have endured subordination and bias due to entrenched patriarchal norms. These challenges stem from cultural biases and unequal

treatment of girl children (Wani et al., 2021). As per the J&K police report, even financially independent and well-educated females face violence due to their perceived inferiority compared to men (as cited in Sarwer, 2017). In Kashmir, females share same destinies and challenges experienced by females globally (Zeeshan & Aliefendioğlu, 2024). Challenging a decadent system and culture has posed significant difficulties for these females (Marchetti & Tocci, 2020) because of fear of additional violence and abuse, exacerbated by a weakened political system that fails to hold criminals and wrongdoers accountable (Maqbool, 2017). Violence impacts these females in several ways leading to reduced female participation in public life, negatively impacting their economic productivity and affecting their physical and mental well-being (Gul, 2015).

Limited research exists on cybercrimes against females in Kashmir. While few studies include Tahir and Sheikh, 2022 address cybercrimes but specific gender perspective remain scarce. An Official report from the Kashmir cyber police station reveals a troubling increase in cybercrimes against females, with 150 complaints recorded in 2020 from the 18-30 age group. Among these, four warranted formal inquiries. The NCRB's 2022 report notes 54 registered cases of cybercrimes against females in J&K, signaling a significant rise from previous years. Experts believe actual figures are likely higher due to societal pressures and fear of reprisal.

Hence in view of the aforementioned literature the present study aims to address this gap by incorporating a gender perspective in the study of cybercrimes. Thus the study focuses on causes, forms and the impact of cybercrimes against female students at university of Kashmir. This crucial research addresses a gap in existing literature on the subject in Kashmir, with findings potentially informing policies and prevention strategies to enhance female's digital safety in their digital world.

IV. Method

Approach and study area

For the present study convergent parallel design is employed. This methodology includes both quantitative and qualitative data within a single study (Classen et al., 2007). It emphasizes gathering, analysing, and integrating both types of data to enhance our comprehension of research problems beyond what either type alone cannot achieve (Bian, 2018), Since relying on a single data source may be insufficient, employing a secondary method becomes necessary

to augment the primary approach, allowing for a more comprehensive explanation of initial findings. The study focused on cybercrimes against females at Kashmir University and its impact on victims. Kashmir University has been chosen because it is the significant educational institution in the region and studying cybercrimes here can provide insights into the experiences of females in higher education setting, which can be a microcosm for the wider society. Also because Kashmir University like other educational institutions have undergone major digital transformation. The widespread use of technology for academic purposes, online communication, and e-learning platforms exposes students (including females) to various cyber risks. Consequently, all participants were females. Previous research has consistently highlighted those females aged 16-35 face heightened vulnerability to cybercrimes (Datta et al., 2020). Therefore this group was deliberately chosen for the study as investigating cybercrimes in this context can provide relevant data for our study. For the quantitative part Questionnaires were shared via Google docs, Email, WhatsApp, and Facebook. The survey questionnaire explicitly communicated the study's purpose to encourage participation. Data collection spanned from 1 January 2022, to 30th April 2022, resulting in 300 responses. However, only 250 complete and consistent responses were considered for analysis, forming the research sample size of 250 participants. For the qualitative part 10 participants agreed to participate for in- depth interview from the same group. So, a total of 10 in-depth interviews provided the qualitative data set for this study. Each interview session ranged from 30 to 40 minutes.

Data collection procedure

A pre-tested questionnaire in English was created, comprising three sections. Section I focused on gathering general profile and basic information from participants. Section II addressed questions related to the causes of cybercrimes, while Section III explored issues and statements concerning cybercrimes and their impact on victims and their coping mechanisms. The questionnaire content was thoroughly examined to ensure the eradication of ambiguous questions. For the qualitative part themes were derived from the same questions posed in the questionnaire. An important aspect of research involves respecting individuals autonomy by allowing them the freedom to choose whether or not to participate. Consent should be obtained without any coercion or pressure (Scheyvens et al., 2003, as cited in Khan et al., 2021). Hence throughout the data collection process, strict confidentiality measures were upheld. The initial section of the questionnaire provided comprehensive details about the study's purpose,

objectives, and informed consent. Participants were explicitly informed that the study focused on evaluating cybercrimes against females. Additionally, participants received clear information about their anonymity and voluntary participation. While acknowledging the inherent limitations of online surveys, we trust in the integrity of participants and assume the accuracy of their responses.

V. Finding and discussion

Female student's exposure to cybercrimes during last one year (2021)

The results reveal that a significant portion of individuals, approximately 84%, encountered some form of cybercrime. When asked about their familiarity with the assailants, a mere 30.9% acknowledged knowing the perpetrator. This suggests that in most cybercrime cases, the attackers remain anonymous to their victims. 67.6% of the participants said that the mode of exposure was mainly through social media and significant portion of participants i.e. 42.8% are not aware about the cybercrimes, cyber laws and cybersecurity. About the types of cybercrimes faced cyber flirting and harassment were significant crimes faced making their proportion to 66.6% and 23% respectively as shown in *table 1*.

Our quantitative data is also supplemented by the qualitative analysis. For instance one participant about the anonymity of the offender revealed that;

“Since I am media student, I express my views a lot online regarding the current issues or political matters. There are some men outside who can't digest that women can have opinion and they kind of troll me (harass) or poke me and whenever I try to get to those accounts they are usually anonymous accounts”.

Offenders hide behind the unknown veils and create fake accounts so that they can't be identified. In this context one participant revealed that;

“Well as far as I can recall, I don't believe a criminal offence has taken place in my life but yes ...I mean I do receive unnecessary messages from persons I don't even know, where they try to act cool or try to initiate conversations”.

When persons receive unwanted messages on daily basis they brush them off as typical internet troll, nothing more than a nuisance. In this regard one participant narrated;

“It started with anonymous messages. At first, they were just annoying rude comments on my posts, strange direct messages from accounts with no profile pictures. However, the messages soon became more frequent and more personal. The anonymity of the offender made it impossible to identify or confront him, creating an eerie sense of being watched”.

The narratives shared by participants highlight the prevalence of online harassment and unwanted attention faced by women. Offenders hide behind the veil of anonymity and troll the persons for expressing their views online. These experiences reveal the complexities of digital communication, where anonymity and gender dynamics intersect. The sheer volume of messages received daily underscores the need for better online safety measures and awareness. And various scholarly studies substantiated the same finding (Balabantaray et al., 2023).

The study showed the significant percentage (42.8%) of participant admitted to having no knowledge of cybercrimes and related legal frameworks, emphasizing the increased vulnerability when using these platforms. In this regard one participant narrated;

“Frankly speaking I have only heard about these terms like cyber laws, cyber security and I have never bothered or inquired about these terms. I know I use lot of social media but I guess I have zero knowledge when it comes to computer literacy and cybersecurity”.

Another participant said:

“It is not a thing to be laughed at, but... I am laughing at myself. I mean, I am a university student, and I should have knowledge about these cyber laws. I spend most of my time online, whether for academic purposes or just entertainment, but I have literally no knowledge about these. Poor me!”

From the conversation it is pertinent to conclude that Participants expressed varying levels of awareness regarding cyber laws and cybersecurity. Participants admitted to having minimal knowledge and no prior inquiry into these terms.

The data further identifies cyber stalking and cyber flirting as most faced types of cybercrimes respectively comprising 23% and 66.6% of the participants. When researchers inquired about the types of cybercrimes faced. One participant said;

“I have messages in my spams where these persons are continuously sending me messages, like “Hi please reply”, “Can we be friends”, “Hi beautiful”, etc. Some even send long paragraphs of shayri and romantic messages. Some are on another level, they chat with themselves”.

Another one responded;

“I remember I used to receive continuous messages from one guy and the messages were always like “Can we talk”, Are you ABC’s friend,” I need your help ’. I replied initially when it was needed but then I ignored that guy because he started irritating me”.

The participant narratives reveal they receive messages on daily basis making this digital space unsafe for them. Two of the most common types of cybercrime are cyber stalking and cyber flirting. Some even report constant and annoying communication. Participants indicate receiving unwanted messages ranging from simple greetings to amorous propositions. These tales highlight the necessity of increased digital awareness and caution when using internet resources. Multiple studies have also identified cyber harassment and cyber flirting as prevalent forms of cyber violence against females. For instance, a survey by Battered Women’s Support Services found that about one-third of participating females had experienced online harassment or cyber flirting (West 2014).

Reasons and consequences of cybercrimes

The data results shed light on the perceived reasons and consequences of cybercrimes. The lack of awareness regarding cyber laws and the proliferation of mobile technology usage were identified with 22.3% and 44.2% respectively as key factors contributing to the rise in cybercrimes. A significant portion of victims, 52.8%, chose to remain silent about their experiences, largely due to fears of being blamed. Responses varied when it came to dealing with cybercrimes. 35.7% of the victims took the initiative to block the offenders. When coming to the mechanism adopted by the participants to save themselves from these crimes notably 27.1 % said we give minimum information and 37.1% said that they change their security to enhance privacy. The psychological toll of cybercrimes was significant, affecting 71.9% of the victims, and 20% reported that these incidents had adversely affected their social lives as shown in **table 2**.

Our quantitative data is also supplemented by the qualitative analysis. For instance when researchers asked about the reasons for increase in cybercrimes. One participant responded;

“Females here don't have so much information about the cyber security and cyber laws. They feel like it's a long process and it's not female friendly. Instead of getting it done by police or any other agency there is the fear that females will be held responsible so they remain silent and suffer in silence”.

Factors for the rise in cybercrimes have been identified as: reduced conviction rate for cybercrimes, a lack of computer literacy, and ignorance of cyber laws. According to the statistics, it's a highly controversial topic in this technologically advanced era. The degree of computer literacy should be much higher given how reliant on technology people are. It would also keep females from being victims of different cybercrimes if they were aware of the numerous cyber laws.

To protect themselves from unnecessary messages and trolling, females often reduce the boundaries of their online space. Often times they choose the audience they want to interact with. They change their privacy setting and let only their close ones to navigate through the privacy wall. In this context one participant said;

“I have seen men literally get mad when they see any female account public .I would get unnecessary and indecent comments on my posts or stories .Then I switched my account to private and only let those people in my safe space who I know and trust fully”.

Sometimes when their patience wears thin, some females resort to blocking the offender. One participant said;

“I can show you, my block list is more as compared to my friend list .what can you expect when your phone starts popping unnecessary all the time .There is only one option left then .I block straight away without giving warning”.

Same experience was shared by another participant. She said;

“I am very confrontational kind of person, I warn them first then block them. And I even tell them that I can trace them even if they are using VPN and yeah I report their accounts sometimes”.

In this research, the typical reactions of females to incidents of cyber violence included blocking the perpetrator, notifying the platform of the offensive content, and updating their contact details. This behaviour is consistent with findings from other studies (Duggan et al., 2014; Pasricha, 2016).

The underreporting of cybercrimes is often linked to the fear of victimization and the associated stigma. Girls frequently endure silently, refraining from reporting incidents due to the anticipated blame directed at them. In this study 52.8% of participants refused to share the encounters because of fear of victimization and stigma. When the researcher inquired about the reasons of silence of victim the participant under review reflected;

“In 2021, I had a best friend and he proposed me for marriage but I declined his marriage proposal citing some genuine reasons from my side. He behaved normally and told me that we will continue to be friends but then he started calling me, messaging me through WhatsApp and other sites and it reached to the level of harassment. I couldn't tell anybody because I thought people would blame me for all this as he was my best friend. There was the fear of stigmatization. So I keep this thing to myself. But when it became torture, I warned him that if this continues I will block him. Even after blocking I would get calls from different numbers and finally. I changed my number to get rid of that person. It was traumatized experience for me”.

From the conversation, it is pertinent to conclude that victims have a fear of stigma and this stigma is associated with cyber abuse which often leads to feelings of shame and social exclusion, further aggravating the trauma experienced by victims (Button & Miller, 2013; Gillett, 2018; Madkour et al., 2014). Consequently, this stigma acts as a barrier to reporting incidents, with many females and marginalized groups choosing silence over seeking justice, as noted by Powell & Henry (2017). The fear of repercussions, such as withdrawal from online engagement and self-harm, is palpable among survivors (van Laer, 2014). Interestingly, none of the victims in our study opted to report the offense to either the police or the women's cell, which the university established to address issues such as harassment and other gender-related challenges.

Cybercrimes can have serious impacts on victims leading to psychological distress, fear, anxiety, and withdrawal from online spaces. Victims often experience difficult emotions like

shame, worthlessness, despair which can manifest in intense emotional distress and interpersonal problems. One participant in this regard said;

“It takes a lot of courage to say these things because of being judged but I guess I have learnt a lot from my past mistakes. I used to like a boy who was of my age .He acted very decent in the beginning and then eventually we end up exchanging our numbers even passwords of our accounts. Things didn’t go well with time and one late night when I tried to get access to my Facebook and Instagram account. I could not get and out of frustration I called my best friend to tell her whether she can see my accounts or not? Since she is from computer sciences she knew about these things”.

The participant took a brief pause, looked down as if she was struggling with words but continued after that. She added;

“She told me that your account has been hacked. I was literally shaking and sweating that time. Although the boy had not uploaded any content there but he did blackmail me for some time. Those days were the most tiring days of my life but eventually I was able to get rid of that person. Thank godhe was psychopath”.

Another one narrated;

“I used to consider myself mentally strong although I am but when you see people making comments and poking you and your work continuously one gets distress full of these men and start low-key hating men .Yeah it gets to that level where it starts affecting your psyche”.

These crimes have not only impacted the victim intrinsically but have also affected their work environment. Victims often need to establish boundaries in their workspaces to avoid encountering the offender on a daily basis. Regarding this one participant revealed;

“One boy from my department approached me but seeing his intensions I straight away confronted him and told him I will block you if he continues to message me. I blocked him after that .But it has affected my social circle in the department. I don’t sit in the grouping where he is present. I try to keep myself aloof and not to encounter him and recently I lost a very good project our professor has given us .only reason was that he was already in the group .So yes! I mean .uhh it feels bad but it has

affected me psychologically because every time I see him it reminds of the incident and it has affected my work as well”.

The accounts highlight the significant psychological effects that cybercrimes have on their victims. Situations like blackmail, harassment, and unceasing criticism cause worry, anxiety, and even trauma. These occurrences can damage mental health by impairing trust, self-worth, and general psychological health. The assessment of cybercrime effects, particularly on female victims, is a critical area of concern. Chaudhary (2019) posits that the escalation of cybercrimes is closely linked to psychological factors. The ramifications for females are multifaceted and profound. Cybercrimes extend beyond causing emotional and psychological distress; they jeopardize personal and professional reputations, lead to financial detriment, and may escalate to physical threats and actual violence (Mishra, 2023). Moreover, the potential for employer discrimination based on one’s online history can have detrimental effects on employment opportunities (Citron, 2014). This susceptibility is reflected in the data, with 71.9% of surveyed victims reporting adverse mental health outcomes as a result of cyber victimization. These psychological effects manifest as anxiety, panic attacks, difficulties in anger management, and an increased propensity for retaliatory desires.

Relation between socio-demographic variables and frequency of exposure to cyber violence among participating females during the last year (2021)

The study’s examination of sociodemographic factors does not reveal any notable correlation except between certain variables like marriage and time spent online. Married females experience it less frequently because of potentially reduced presence on social media and a more cautious approach to online interactions. More time spent means more susceptible to cybercrimes so the researcher has clubbed it into the following themes.

Marital status and risk perception

When individuals get married, their responsibilities increase significantly. As a result, they often reduce their screen time and prioritize family and work-related tasks. This reduced exposure to online platforms can lead to a decreased risk perception of cybercrimes. To overview the effects of marriage on risk perception one participant stated;

“Life changed significantly after marriage. Prior to getting married, I was quite active on social media platforms. However, my screen time has reduced considerably

due to the responsibilities I have now. I can't afford to be idle and scroll aimlessly all day. Consequently, my exposure to cybercrimes is minimal because I don't have much time to spend on social media".

Another girl who was recently married and was in third year of research said;

"My research work and marriage responsibilities have kept me away from the current world, I suppose. I hardly find time to connect with my friends and relatives online. After marriage, it seems we can't engage in random chitchat with strangers online. We must draw a line and prioritize what is important and fruitful".

As a daughter-in-law and a mother, your roles evolve, impacting how you interact with others online. You may distance yourself from behaviours that would not please your in-laws. In this context one participant stated;

"Living with my in-laws and caring for my small child demands my full attention. I prioritize my family and research, and I am selective about responding to messages and calls only when they are relate to my research. After marriage, there is an expectation to maintain a certain behaviour to stay in the good graces of the in-laws. Being constantly on the phone and chatting with strangers isn't feasible".

These narratives demonstrate how marriage has a big influence on people's internet behaviour. Due to marital duties, participants report using screens less frequently, which reduces their exposure to cybercrimes. After marriage, it becomes crucial to put family and studies ahead of sporadic online connections, highlighting the necessity of striking a balance between personal and digital life.

Time Spent Online and Vulnerability

When individuals spend significant time online, their vulnerability to cybercrimes increases. Openness in sharing personal details, connecting with strangers, and frequent engagement on social media platforms can inadvertently expose them to various. **When inquired about the time spent online and vulnerability one participant under review reflected;**

"I spent my day and night on phone. My eyes literally trace the contours of virtual landscapes. Messaging apps, and online forums. My life unfolds in pixels likes, shares, and retweets. But with every click, I unwittingly steps into the maze of

cybercrimes. My vulnerability is in my openness and the time I waste on media platforms. I shares personal details, posts my whereabouts, and connect with strangers. The more I expose, the wider the door swings open for cyber threats”.

Similar experiences were shared by another participant of the same age. She said;

“My days used to revolve around screens: social media, messaging apps, and virtual communities. I would shares joys, sorrows, and mundane moments with an invisible audience. My life would unfold in status updates, emojis, and filtered snapshots. But beneath the surface lies a hidden cost. I would get disgusting messages from strangers, it had taken toll on my mental health but then my guardian suggested me to reduce your screen time and if possible don't be social media for some time .His suggestion worked and now I do use social media but now I rarely receive any unwanted messages”.

These narratives highlight how digital platforms have a ubiquitous influence on our lives. With an audience that cannot see them, participants share intimate moments and facts about their days spent hunched over screens. Openness has a price, too, as it exposes oneself to online attacks. Some people's mental health has been impacted by receiving unsettling communications from strangers. Reducing screen time as advised by a guardian has resulted in fewer unsolicited communications, emphasizing the significance of balancing online activity. Similar findings have emerged from other studies, with Arafa et al. (2018) and Arafa and Senosy (2017) observing a significant relationship between the amounts of time spent online daily and the risk and frequency of cyber violence encounters. Consistent with the findings of Winkelman et al. (2015), which highlighted a significant correlation between age and the likelihood of receiving threats via text or instant messaging, this study further explores the relationship between marital status and vulnerability to cybercrimes. Our research indicates that single students are more frequently targeted by cybercrimes compared to married students. This disparity can be partly attributed to the differing online presence between these two groups. Married, engrossed in their responsibilities, tend to have limited online interactions, thereby reducing their exposure to potential cyber threats. In contrast, single students, who are less encumbered by obligations and responsibilities, exhibit a higher degree of online activity, which inadvertently increases their risk of encountering cyber violence as can be seen in *table 3*.

VI. Conclusion

In summary, while the prevalence of cybercrimes in the region is not considered severe, females regularly encounter various forms of online abuse, including cyberstalking, unsolicited advances, and harassment. There is a crucial gap in awareness regarding cybercrimes, which is a major factor leading to the increase in such offenses. The lack of adequate cybersecurity education further exacerbates the issue. Online discrimination against women is a reflection of broader societal discrimination, now manifesting in the form of cybercrimes. The reluctance to report these crimes is notable, often rooted in the fear of victim-blaming, which silences the affected individuals. The anonymity of the offenders, along with the lack of strict enforcement and resources for cybercrime investigation, also hinders the reporting process. The widespread risk of cyber violence impacts females irrespective of the amount of time they spend online, highlighting the need to understand its effects on the victims. The apprehension of being blamed and socially ostracized leads too many incidents going unreported, and concerns about family honour may further contribute to the suppression of these cases. Consequently, victims may suffer from mental health issues, such as depression and anxiety, and may withdraw from online engagement to avoid the repercussions associated with victim-blaming.

Thus it becomes imperative to enact robust cybercrime laws, enhance digital literacy, and foster a supportive environment. This includes integrating online safety education into the university's curriculum, establishing a support system for victims, and promoting research to understand the scope of cyber violence. Additionally, societal attitudes towards cyber violence must be challenged through media campaigns, and a collaborative approach involving various stakeholders should be adopted to ensure a safe digital space for females.

Limitations

The study primarily focused female students at the University of Kashmir, resulting in a relatively limited sample size which might affect the reliability and generalizability of the findings. Additionally, the data collected were based on self-reported experiences and perceptions, which can be subjective and influenced by personal biases or inaccuracies in recall.

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Table 1

Questions	Responses	Number	Percentage%
Exposed to cybercrimes	Yes	210	84
	No	40	16
Number of times exposed to Cybercrimes	once	71	33.8
	Twice	49	23.3
	More than twice	90	42.8
Do you know the offender?	Yes	65	30.9
	No	145	69
Mode of exposure	email	5	2.3
	Mobile phone	63	30
	Social media	142	67.6
	Other	0	0
Aware of cybercrimes, cyber Laws and cybersecurity	slightly	65	30.9
	completely	55	26.1
	Not aware	90	42.8
Types of cybercrimes faced	Cyberstalking	2	0.9
	Harassment	63	23

Cyber defamation	0	0
Morphing	0	0
Email spoofing	0	0
Hacking	5	2.3
Cyber flirting	140	66.6

Source: *Fieldwork (2022)*

Table 2

Questions	Responses	Number	percentage%
Reasons for increase in Cybercrimes	Lack of computer literacy	26	12.3
	Ignorance of cyber laws	47	22.3
	Increased mobile and internet use	93	44.2
	Unemployment of educated youth	23	10.9
	Lower conviction rate for cybercrimes	21	10
Reasons for silence of Cybercrime victim	Not aware of cybersecurity laws	36	17.1
	Fear of victim-blaming	111	52.8
	Fear of isolation	38	18.0
	Non-accessibility to cyber police Station	25	11.9
Action taken in case Of harassment	Block	75	35.7
	Report	33	15.7
	Ignore	39	18.5
	Warning and blocked	42	20
	Stopped using social media	21	10
Mechanism to protect on social media	Give minimum information	57	27.1
	Change security settings to	78	37.1

	Enhance privacy		
	Adjust information depending	48	22.8
	On trust level		
	Use dummy email accounts	27	12.8
Impact of cybercrime on Victim	Psychological	151	71.9
	Social	42	20
	Economical	17	8.0
	No effect	0	0

Source: *Fieldwork (2022)*

Table 3**Socio demographic variables frequency of exposure to cybercrimes during last year**

	Not exposed		Exposed	
	n	%	n	%
Age group				
≤27	28	70	112	53.3
>27	12	30	98	46.6
Marital status				
Single	13	32.5	145	69.0
Married	27	67.5	65	30.9
Divorced	0	0	0	0
Widow	0	0	0	0
Educational level				
Post graduate	15	37.5	120	57.1
Scholars	25	62.5	90	42.8
Residence				
Rural	22	55	131	62.3
Urban	18	45	79	37.6
Mobile phone and internet usage (h/day)				
0 - 1 h	20	50	20	9.5

1-2 h	10	25	33	15.7
2-3 h	8	20	69	32.8
Above 3	2	5	88	41.9

Source: *Fieldwork* (2022)
